

Moderating effect of Social Media Usage on Technology Barriers to Technology Adoption by Teachers

Genimon V Joseph*¹ and Kennedy Andrew Thomas²

¹School of Management Studies, Christ University, Bangalore- 560029

²CEDBEC, Christ University, Bangalore- 560029

¹jinuachan@gmail.com, ²kennedy.andrew@christuniversity.in

Abstract

The education and learning process is redefined with the mesmerizing impact of ever-volatile technology platforms. With the advent of the Industry 4.0, supported by the intelligent web 3.0 connectivity catalyzed the transformation of traditional education philosophies and pedagogies in tune with the Learning 4.0, to empower both learners and educators as co-producers of knowledge. The researches brought to light that social application platforms became an indispensable part of the digital learning process. The bio-inspired technology designs considerably cast off the issues related to ease of use, perceived usefulness, and reduced the perceived internal barriers of the teachers to improve their Technology Adoption substantially. This Technology Adoption research was conducted under the theoretical framework of the 'education change model' of Michael Fullan integrated with educators' Communities of Practice. This descriptive research study framed to address how the teachers' Technology Adoption was affected by their use of social media platforms and how it moderated their perceived Technology Barriers. Standardized questionnaires from Joe W. Kotrlik and Donna H. Redmann were adopted with a pilot study. Stratified cluster sampling was used to gather 1029 responses from Higher Secondary School teachers of six educational districts in Kerala. The analysis was done with IBM SPSS v.21 and Process v.3.4. Teachers' Social Media Use and Perceived Technology Barriers were significantly correlated with the Technology Adoption of the teachers. The perceived Technology Barriers were reduced with respect to their Social Media Usage. The relation of perceived Technology Barriers with Technology Adoption was significantly moderated with Social Media Use. Gender and school sectors were neither mediated nor moderated Technology Adoption. These results are helpful in the teachers' technology training programs and for further research.

Keywords: Social Media Use, Technology Adoption, Technology Barrier, Learning Environments

1. Introduction

Technology development supported with the intelligent systems redefines the world swifter than ever expected and the facelift from web2.0 to semantic web3.0 not only empowered the industrial leap, but it even rejuvenates the overall social life of the people. The technology platforms, cutthroat marketing-service aspects, customer perspectives, education scenarios, and even almost all production processes are integrating the intelligent facilities brought through the Artificial Intelligence (AI) platforms. The web3.0 becomes the solid substratum for rendezvousing the ubiquitous technology requirement for Industry4.0 by providing collective intelligence through connecting data, concepts, applications, and ultimately people [1]. The 4th generation industry is consisted of 'Cyber-Physical Systems' with the physical world seamlessly connected with the virtual world and the cloud supported virtual reality systems. These technological innovations are the ramifications of the industry development and the new Education4.0 system expected to be essentially tuned with technical, methodological, social, and personal competencies of these technological advancements to mold future industry leaders [2]-[4]. Studies brought to light that education scenario is normally immune to change with respect to the other industry sectors across time and the chasm widens as the industry converges into the unfathomed technology-driven arenas

Deliberate attempts were made worldwide in the top-down model to tackle the benefit of the technology advancements for the learning process. In order to accelerate the technology integration in the digital teaching-learning process, social media tools were readily incorporated as the ancillary learning technologies, which even elevated the technologically empowered learners as the co-

producers of knowledge [5]-[7]. Social media were readily incorporated into the learning process by the learners and the Digital Learning Environments (DLEs) were appreciated promptly in student circles [3], [8]. However, educators' lag in Technology Adoption remained as a hurdle for the ease of technology implementation in the educational scenario and their digital citizenship needed to be better formed with knowledge, skill, and digital behaviors [9]- [10].

2. Technology Adoption in Education

The Technology Adoption process exhibits a fluctuating nature over the years and many studies were made to understand the determinants of the technology diffusion process. The complex process of technology diffusion was systematically studied by Gabriel Tarde in 1903, connected with the technology diffusion in agriculture fields, and after that, by Friedrich Ratzel and Leo Frobenius. However, their creative insights were not immediately followed with empirical studies on diffusion [11]. The 'Innovation Diffusion Theory' (IDT) of Everett Rogers (1965) and subsequent deliberations through the Diffusion of Innovation (1995) had initiated a solid foundation for further studies related to the technology diffusion process [12]. These studies discussed the acceptance of particular technology concerning the perceived usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), while subsequent researches stressed the further parameters of the Technology Adoption process [13]-[14].

Multiple theories of Technology Adoption were emerged with the technology explosion era as the features of the technology itself underwent drastic changes. Technology feature-based theories were later rolled back to user-centric behaviorist models. Consolidation of the multiple theoretical frames were brought through Unified Theory of Adoption and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model, Concern Based Adoption Model (CBAM), social learning theories, and cognitive learning models which explained multiple aspects of the adoption process with respect to the fluidity of the technology platforms [12]-[13], [15]-[17]. These studies provided varied insights for the policymakers of technology implementation to consider those influential factors. Many of the educational technology studies were done with respect to the implementation of specific educational technologies and most often, the thematization of the studies got restricted as the individual aspects of the technology itself had a decisive impact on its adoption in the education sector. With the grounded support of the semantic web3.0 facilities, the technology features itself were simultaneously modified to suit the demands of individualized customers, with the real-time feedbacks collected through the user data, crash-bug reports, and usage patterns [14], [18]-[19].

The education Technology Adoption models discussed above were concentrating on different dimensions of the adoption process, which were constantly refined along with the corresponding technology modifications [14], [20]. In general, education Technology Adoption was initiated by the introduction of specific technology platforms in the teaching-learning systems, incorporated gradually, and continued through the participation of teacher-student collaborations [21]-[22]. The Technology Adoption as per the 'education change model' (innovation-focused approach) of Michael Fullan (2007) is usually accomplished through the stages of adoption, implementation, and continuation, which bring forth desirable outcomes. Adoption phase characterized by contact with technology, familiarity with features, and initial usage. In the implementation stage, the technology systems are amalgamated with the teaching process and continued in the last stage [23]-[24]. Education Technology Adoption studies by Joe W. Kotrlik and Donna H. Redmann (2009) and others adopted this education change model in their scale development to analyze the specific educational Technology Adoption [24]. This study used this conceptual frame and scale for gathering the data for this Technology Adoption study

3. Technology Adoption and Technology Barriers

The studies on the Technology Adoption process brought to light that the adoption process could be considerably interrupted through Technology Barriers [25]-[27]. Technology Barriers were broadly classified as external and internal barriers of the Technology Adoption process. External Technology Barriers are termed as first-order barriers (physical barriers) and the internal barriers are termed as the

second-order (psychological) barriers. Certain authors, as Chin-Chung Tsai and Ching Sing Chai (2012) refer to the third-order barriers related to teachers' impediments in 'design thinking'. Psychological barriers are considerably addressed through the regular system modifications, user interface adaptation with 'bio-inspired and bio-metric designs', and also with user modification options built into the technology platforms [19], [28]. The primary or physical barriers were rather reduced with the availability of computer systems in the schools and the widespread use of mobile gadgets. However, the perceived first-order barriers related to the institutional and technical assistance systems, lesser quality of technology accessibility and time allocated for the technology-based learning process, and lack of technology mastering through proper training are inflicting blockage for the Technology Adoption process. The Technology Adoption process is stagnated due to the presence of these inhibiting factors [27]-[28]. The Technology Adoption studies needed to consider these factors and address the pathways to reduce the impact of these perceived Technology Barriers.

4. Social Media on Technology Adoption

An instructional paradigm shift is explicit in technology-based education systems with the boom of new generation technologies especially, with social media and with its ubiquitous acceptance across the globe. Flexibility in accommodating changes through the blending of the conventional face-to-face model with e-learning models became vital in the new education system. These pedagogical shifts that occurred in educational transformations were significantly powered by the social learning models amalgamated with affective, cognitive, and contextual learning concerns [28]. Most often, these educational learning technologies were introduced in top-down models from the educational policy formulators to teachers, as in the case of interactive whiteboards, simulation labs, software utilization, and other learning technology platforms. Whereas social media was introduced in the learning space in a bottom-up fashion, spontaneously incorporated by students, moved upward to teachers, and then to education systems [5], [29]. Social media is considered as the overwhelming supporting platform for shared-learning, fosters learning motivation and engagement with convenience, maintain collaborative learning with virtual connectedness, and provides informal social learning environment (SLE) with virtual personal learning gadgets [28].

As social media is catering to the essential societal nature of connectedness, its adoption falls natural to its uses, which is most often lacking in the educational technology platforms, solely created for learning purposes with its intricacies. Studies made on the impact of social media on students learning brought to light that collaborative social-learning enhanced when done under the educators' supervision. The monitored use of social media for academic purpose accelerated Technology Adoption, participatory digital learning culture, enhanced higher order of learning skills and reduced the reach-out problems beyond the academic timings, improved instructors learning technology usage, improved collaborative learning of the educators with their peers, and enhanced depth and spread of the learning process [5], [8], [30]. Educators, due to their 'digital immigrant' nature in Technology Adoption, prefer social media learning models than the intricated technology backdrops provided for the prescribed curriculum. It is researched that, regular use of social media reduces the technology anxiety and perceived external-internal Technology Barriers of the educators and enhance the learning through social collaboration [5], [26], [30].

The social media-based collaborative e-learning and Technology Adoption had a solid foundation in the social learning theories, which affirmed that learning takes place as the result of social experience [21]. The knowledge creation as per the Constructivist approach was imparted through learner's experiences and interactions. Piaget's Cognitive Constructivism and Vygotsky's Social Constructivism suggested a cognitive and social dimension to the knowledge creation, respectively [31]-[32]. Based on this social learning background, Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger (1991) affirmed that the learning process was enhanced through collaborative practice and participation called 'Communities of Practice'(CoP) or 'situated learning'. Educators' Communities of Practice through social media usage were found to be increased their technological collaboration and reduced their inhibitions to the learning technology platforms [31]-[32].

5. Social Media and Technology Barriers

Social media usage and its integration into the learning environment had a significant role in acquiring the skills of 'Digital Citizenship' in the modern world. The familiarity with social media and using its multiple interface options provided confidence to the educators to use the other learning technology platforms similar to the social media interfaces [5], [8], [21]. Social media not only facilitated the learning process but, in turn, due to its innate features of sociability in user interfaces, permeated beyond the boundaries of multiple Technology Barriers. Social media was most often associated with the new generation of mobile gadgets, which was offering excellent performance than the confined learning systems [7].

Due to the overwhelming capacity of platform indifferent operations, these media could also support the cutting-edge digital learning resource as in MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) or other Small Private Online Courses (SPOC) effectively [8], [28]. This platform-indifferent feature of the social learning systems could considerably reduce the disparity in the physical distribution of the computing systems and increased the productive learning time dramatically. The social media and mobile interfaces were even more integrated closely to serve as the unified system for e-commerce, daily digital payment systems, news streaming, information search, and social communication platforms within a single-window [33]. The communication chasm between the learner-learned became narrowed down as the learning could be extended beyond the academic schedule and the school peripheries with the adequate use of virtual learning environments [34]. The learning technology diffused in an unhindered, dynamic, interactive, user-friendly, and user-centered fashion with the ubiquitous application of social media facilities. It provided a technology-enriched platform for self-directed professional development for educators and learners beyond the physical barriers of time and space [14].

Social media related studies were multitude around the globe, which addressed its impact on societal learning realms; however, fewer studies were done to identify the effects of teachers' social media use on their Technology Adoption [6], [30], [35]. This study is relevant not only as it addresses the less explored gap of social media use and Technology Adoption, but it even more relevant as the mobile gadgets and social media platforms were becoming intertwined with all walks of day-to-day life [13], [35]. This transformative amalgamation virtually disrupted all the traditional conceptual boundaries of the learning premises, business transactions, societal presence, and widely opened the unfathomed space of creativity and learning around the clock. This research is thus, modeled to identify how the educators' use of social media impacts their Technology Adoption in the academic scenario. This study also intended to understand the digital technology-enabled learning environments of the HSSs of Kerala state. This descriptive study addresses the research questions:

1. What is the extent of Technology Adoption and Technology Barriers in educators?
2. Whether educators' social media use increases their Technology Adoption? and
3. Whether social media use help the educators to overcome their perceived Technology Barriers?

6. Research Design

This research is conducted among Higher Secondary School (HSS) teachers of the northern part of Kerala State, India, under the State syllabus and center syllabus curriculum. The Indian education sector is known for its technology-enabled pedagogy. The technology leadership of the Kerala State is known as the 'Kerala model' which is imparted in the state curriculum through the auspicious leadership of Kerala Infrastructure and Technology for Education (KITE) under Kerala State education department [6], [29], [36]. The technology infrastructure with seamless data support and regular teacher training on digital pedagogies are the exemplary features of the KITE model. The HSSs with center curriculum also anchored around digital learning systems with multimedia right from the pre-schools.

A preliminary study was conducted with students, administrators, and teachers to gather information related to Technology Adoption and the influence of social media on technology usage. The research tools were tested through a pilot study. The participants of this study were Higher Secondary School teachers distributed across the six educational districts of the Malabar area, under

the Kerala State. Samples were collected in a stratified cluster model with HSSs stratified as Government HSS, Aided HSS, Un-Aided HSS, and center syllabus HSS. After the preliminary analysis of the samples collected, 1029 responses of the teachers were found complete for analysis. The sample consisted of 67.3% females, 91.1% were Post Graduated with specializations as Arts (25.9%), Science (36.9%), Language (21.3%), and commerce and others (15.8%). The samples were distributed rather proportionally in six educational districts under the four school strata. The data were treated as normal with the Skewness (± 1.06) and Kurtosis (± 2.1) within the accepted limits as ± 2 and ± 3 , respectively [37].

The survey instrument items were adopted from the scale developed by Joe W. Kotrlik and Donna H. Redmann (2009) to analyze the perceived academic Technology Adoption and Technology Barriers. The Technology Adoption scale consisted of 15-items and the Technology Barriers scale consisted of 7-items [24]. 5-point Likert scale is adopted to gather the responses as 1= Not at all agree, 5= strongly agree. Social media use data was collected as a self-reported mode with 8-items. The tools were reaffirmed with the reliability value of Cronbach's alpha for Technology Adoption as 0.757 with inter-item variance ± 0.007 , for Technology Barriers as 0.865 with inter-item variance ± 0.01 , and for Social Media Use as 0.868 with inter-item variance ± 0.02 .

7. Results

The data were analyzed with SPSS v.21 and the Process v3.4 macro developed by Andrew Hayes (Hayes, 2017). A total of 1090 responses was received and 1029 responses were complete for analysis. Based on the research questions, the following analysis was done.

7.1 Technology Infrastructure, Training, Technology Adoption, and Technology Barriers

The preliminary discussions made with the educators, students, and the administrative staff of the Higher Secondary Schools (HSSs) understudy has revealed that digital technology-based learning environments were well adopted in schools. Kerala State syllabus Aided and Government HSSs were equipped with ICT enabled classrooms under the government-funded project called 'Hi-Tech School Project' throughout the Kerala state. The classrooms were equipped with laptops, whiteboards, multimedia projectors with sound systems, hi-speed data connectivity through a center education server with education database, lab with LCD TVs HD Cams, printers, and UPS. Regular technology training was done under the KITE- Kerala and the Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) were almost fully utilized in schools. The Kerala State is appreciated for the most massive deployment of the FOSS in education and hands-on technology training sessions were provided through trainer training programs, master trainee programs through regional KITE district nodal centers, and online platforms. The center syllabus schools also fully equipped with ICT enabled learning environments and regular training. Teachers are using social media and mobile gadgets for their personal and professional needs.

The teachers were experiencing below average Technology Barriers ($\mu = 2.46$ with $\sigma = 0.665$) and slightly high Technology Adoption ($\mu = 3.74$ $\sigma = 0.592$) in a five-point Likert scale. The Analysis of Variance (one-way ANOVA) showed that educators' Technology Adoption and Technology Barriers are not showing significant variance across the demographical parameters; however, Technology Barriers showed a significant variance across the school categories (with $df = 3$, $f = 2.747$ $p = 0.042$).

7.2 Social Media use and educators' Technology Adoption

The Analysis of Variance (one-way ANOVA) showed that educators' use of mobile-based social media was varied across the age groups (with $df = 3$, $f = 4.366$ $p = 0.005$), WhatsApp, Search (Google) and voice calls were highly used for the communication and information. The split analysis on age basis showed that the social media use was more among teachers below 30 years and Instagram was very frequent among them. Social media conference calls, ShareChat, Flicker, Snapchat were least used by the teachers and those above 40 years never used those. It is to be noted that SMS use was

reduced considerably with the spread of social media. Table-1, given below, listed the major five social media used by teachers with mean and deviation with respect to the age groups.

Table 1. Social Media use across the age groups: mean with deviation

Media	Below 30 years (Mean \pm SD)	30-39years (Mean \pm SD)	40-49 years (Mean \pm SD)	50 years and above (Mean \pm SD)
WhatsApp	4.66 \pm 1.698	4.27 \pm 1.625	4.17 \pm 1.580	3.85 \pm 1.705
YouTube	3.27 \pm 1.815	2.39 \pm 1.665	2.44 \pm 1.645	2.28 \pm 1.647
Face Book	3.26 \pm 1.938	3.12 \pm 1.712	2.84 \pm 1.630	2.48 \pm 1.704
Instagram	1.39 \pm .919	1.33 \pm .817	1.37 \pm .886	1.17 \pm .434
SMS apps	2.32 \pm .1.240	2.55 \pm 1.380.	2.58 \pm 1.413.	2.32 \pm .1.183

Educators' social media use explained 14.2% of their Technology Adoption on correlation analysis (Pearson Correlation, $r = 0.142$, $p = 0.000$ at 0.01 level, 2tailed). It was also noted that the Technology Adoption at the center curriculum, Government schools, aided schools, and unaided were somewhat similar under the study and the correlation with respect to demography was not showing any significant trend.

7.3 Social Media use and Educators' Technology Barriers

The perceived Technology Barriers were below average ($\mu = 2.45$ $\sigma = 0.665$) and were in incremental nature with respect to the age groups shown as in table-2 below. Social media use and Technology Barriers were rather in inverse proportion.

The social media use and Technology Adoption were negatively correlated with significant p -value (Pearson Correlation, $r = -0.122$, $p = 0.000$ at 0.01 level, 2tailed). Educators' perceived Technology Barriers may be reduced by 12.2% with their social media usage.

Table 2. Social Media use across the age groups and Technology Barriers: mean with deviation and Pearson Correlation

	Below 30 years	30-39years	40-49 years	50 years and above
Technology Barriers	$\mu = 2.37$ $\sigma = .651$	$\mu = 2.446$ $\sigma = .655$	$\mu = 2.47$ $\sigma = .677$	$\mu = 2.52$ $\sigma = .654$
Mean Social Media use	$\mu = 2.509$ $\sigma = .699$	$\mu = 2.317$ $\sigma = .66$	$\mu = 2.296$ $\sigma = .65$	$\mu = 2.16$ $\sigma = .709$
Correlation b/w Technology Barriers and Technology Adoption	$r = .460$, $p = .000$	$r = .460$, $p = .000$	$r = .569$, $p = .000$	$r = .581$, $p = .000$

7.4 Moderating effect of Social Media Use on Technology Barriers to Technology Adoption

Moderating effect of the social media on Technology Barriers to Technology Adoption were tested with the "Process v3.4" macro for SPSS-21, developed Andrew Hayes (Hayes, 2017). The regression analysis indicated that the educators' Technology Adoption was significantly moderated by social media usage ($r = 0.5348$, $r^2 = 0.2860$, $MSE = 0.2510$, $F = 136.8453$, $df (3,1025)$, $p = 0.016$) and moderated by the age of the teachers ($\beta = 0.0172$, $se = 0.003$, $p = 0.028$). The table-3 provided the bootstrapped moderation impact of social media use on Technology Barriers to Technology Adoption ($\beta = 0.1223$, $se = 0.0424$) as significant to the teachers. The educators' social media usage enabled them to adopt the technology better way. The social media use has a negative direct moderation effect on Technology Adoption ($\beta = -0.2532$, $p = 0.0147$). The regression analysis of educators' perceived Technology Barriers predicted negatively by social media use in a significant manner ($\beta = -0.323$, $se = 0.158$, $p = .000$), and without moderation, it predicted negatively ($\beta = -0.6900$). The test of highest

order unconditional interaction between Technology Barrier and social media use was also significant ($r^2\text{-chng}= 0.0058$, $F= 8.3196$, $df (1, 1025)$, $p= 0.0040$) among teachers. It was also affirmed that teachers' Technology Adoption was not significantly mediated by their social media use ($\beta= 0.0007$, $\text{BootSE}= .0036$, $\text{Boot LLCI}= -.0063$, $\text{BootULCI}= .0083$). It was thus affirmed that when moderated with social media use, educators could considerably reduce their perceived Technology Barriers in the Technology Adoption process. The results of this study support earlier researchers [26]-[27].

Table 3: Moderation effect of Social media on Tech Barrier to tech Adoption

	coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	5.3554	0.1999	26.7938	.0000	4.9632	5.7476
Tech Barrier	-0.6900	0.0805	-8.5760	.0000	-.8478	-.5321
Social Media	-.2532	.1036	-2.4440	.0147	-.4565	-.0499
Tech Barrier x Social Media	.1223	.0424	2.8844	.0040	.0391	.2056

8. Conclusion

This descriptive study on the Technology Adoption of the educators with respect to their perceived Technology Barriers and social media use showed that the Technology Adoption was considerably influenced by their social media use, Technology Barriers and age. Teaching-learning technology environments were available and apt regular technology training were provided to the educators. FOSS and associated learning technologies were provided to teachers during the KITE-Kerala training programs. Teachers' perceived Technology Barriers were reduced with the use of social media. The educators' social media use was varying across the age groups and Technology Barriers were slightly increased with respect to their age. There was no significant difference between educators' Technology Adoption with respect to different HSS categories. The gender indifference in Technology Adoption and perceived Technology Barriers among teachers were affirmed in this study [18]. These were brought through the intensive technology training provided to the teachers across schools and the user-friendly nature of the technology platforms. Gender impact was explicit, while the technology applications were complex with less technology training. The research also affirmed the utilization of integrated learning environments with media apps, as social media usage has undergone unimaginable swift with the rapid penetration of smartphone gadgets. With the advent of the web3.0 intelligent services, the mobile platforms integrated with social media technology not only just became par with the computer systems, but rather surpass the traditional laptops and localized systems in their overwhelming use, convenience, and even performance. Further researches on educators' learning 4.0 skills are needed with respect to their technology affinity and the Technology Adoption to the ever-evolving flux of the social media-mobile technology models and its applications in socio-economical fields.

Acknowledgments

This research received no funding from any agencies and was done with proper permission as per the code of research ethics.

Reference

- Han, L. (2018, December). Analysis of New Advances in the Application of Artificial Intelligence to Education. In *2018 3rd International Conference on Education, E-learning and Management Technology (EEMT 2018)*. Atlantis Press.
- Mourtzis, D. (2018, June). Development of Skills and Competences in Manufacturing Towards Education 4.0: A Teaching Factory Approach. In *International Conference on the Industry 4.0 model for Advanced Manufacturing* (pp. 194-210). Springer, Cham.

03. Salloum, S. A., Mhamdi, C., Al Kurdi, B., & Shaalan, K. (2018). Factors affecting the Adoption and Meaningful Use of Social Media: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *International Journal of Information Technology*, 2(3), 96-109.
04. Mourtzis, D., Vlachou, E., Dimitrakopoulos, G., & Zogopoulos, V. (2018). Cyber-physical systems and education 4.0—the teaching factory 4.0 concept. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 23, 129-134.
05. Greenhow, C., & Lewin, C. (2016). Social media and education: Reconceptualizing the boundaries of formal and informal learning. *Learning, media and technology*, 41(1), 6-30.
06. Pettersson, F. (2018). On the issues of digital competence in educational contexts—a review of literature. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(3), 1005-1021.
07. Xu, S., Yang, H. H., MacLeod, J., & Zhu, S. (2019). Social media competence and digital citizenship among college students. *Convergence*, 25(4), 735-752.
08. Almansour, N. A. A. (2019). *Educational uses of social media in learning by university students* (Order No. 13807127). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (2269961854). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2269961854?accountid=38885>
09. Choi, M., Cristol, D., & Gimbert, B. (2018). Teachers as digital citizens: The influence of individual backgrounds, internet use and psychological characteristics on teachers' levels of digital citizenship. *Computers & Education*, 121, 143-161.
10. Naydanova, E., Beal, B. D., & Doty, D. H. (2018). Internet Use for School-Mandated and Self-Initiated Learning: Good, Bad, or Both?. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 21(7), 444-449.
11. Beliaevsky, N. (2006). Revisiting Vygotsky and Gardner: realizing human potential. *Journal of Aesthetic Education*, 1-11.
12. Taherdoost, H. (2018). A review of technology acceptance and adoption models and theories. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 22, 960-967.
13. López-Nicolás, C., Molina-Castillo, F. J., & Bouwman, H. (2008). An assessment of advanced mobile services acceptance: Contributions from TAM and diffusion theory models. *Information & Management*, 45(6), 359-364.
14. Breen, P. (2018). Resources and Technology Use. In *Developing Educators for The Digital Age: A Framework for Capturing Knowledge in Action* (pp. 101-114). London: University of Westminster Press. Retrieved from www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv5vddjh.10
15. Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-hall.
16. Bandura, A. (2009). Social cognitive theory of mass communication. In *Media effects* (pp. 110-140). Routledge.
17. Bandura, A. (2014). Social cognitive theory of moral thought and action. In *Handbook of moral behavior and development* (pp. 69-128). Psychology Press.
18. Sang, G., Valcke, M., Van Braak, J., & Tondeur, J. (2010). Student teachers' thinking processes and ICT integration: Predictors of prospective teaching behaviors with educational technology. *Computers & Education*, 54(1), 103-112.
19. Galer, M., Harker, S., Ziegler, J., & Galer, M. (Eds.). (2016). *Methods and tools in user-centred design for information technology* (Vol. 9). Elsevier.
20. Straub, E. T. (2009). Understanding Technology Adoption: Theory and future directions for informal learning. *Review of educational research*, 79(2), 625-649.
21. Domingo, M. G., & Garganté, A. B. (2016). Exploring the use of educational technology in primary education: Teachers' perception of mobile technology learning impacts and applications' use in the classroom. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 56, 21-28.
22. Kearney, M., Schuck, S., Aubusson, P., & Burke, P. F. (2018). Teachers' Technology Adoption and practices: lessons learned from the IWB phenomenon. *Teacher Development*, 22(4), 481-496.
23. Bahçekapili, T. (2018). *An Investigation of I: 1 technology initiative through the lens of Fullan's educational change model: a three-year study* (Doctoral dissertation, Middle East Technical University).
24. Kotrlik, J. W., & Redmann, D. H. (2009). Technology Adoption for Use in Instruction by Secondary Technology Education Teachers. *Journal of Technology Education*, 21(1), 44-59.
25. Kopcha, T. J. (2012). Teachers' perceptions of the barriers to technology integration and practices with technology under situated professional development. *Computers & Education*, 59(4), 1109-1121.
26. Kilinc, E., Tarman, B., & Aydin, H. (2018). Examining turkish social studies teachers' beliefs about barriers to Technology integration. *TechTrends*, 62(3), 221-223.
27. Sánchez-Prieto, J. C., Hernández-García, Á., García-Peñalvo, F. J., Chaparro-Peláez, J., & Olmos-Migueláñez, S. (2019). Break the walls! Second-Order barriers and the acceptance of mLearning by first-year pre-service teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 95, 158-167.
28. Hamsan, S. N. A., Aziz, M. A., & Taslim, J. (2018). Educators' Readiness in using Mobile Phone as a Pedagogical Tool for Teaching. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(4.31), 459-464.

28. Nagel, J. K. (2019). Preliminary findings from a comparative study of two bio-inspired design methods in a second-year engineering curriculum. In *2019 ASEE Annual Conference and Expo*.
29. Nayar, A. (2018). *Teaching and Learning in Technology Empowered Classrooms—Issues, Contexts and Practices*. Partridge Publishing.
30. Joseph, Genimon V & Thomas, Kennedy A (2020). Volatility of Digital Technology Enabled Learning through Social Media: Educators' Apprehensions. *Test Engineering and Management*. 82. (Pp. 5832–5839). 10.6084/m9.figshare.11847258.
31. Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge university press.
32. Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: learning, meaning, and identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi: 10.1017/cbo9780511803932
33. Cao, Y., Ajjan, H., & Hong, P. (2013). Using social media applications for educational outcomes in college teaching: A structural equation analysis. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 44(4), 581-593.
34. Gardner, H. (2011). *Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligences*. New York,
35. Chugh, R., & Ruhi, U. (2018). Social media in higher education: A literature review of Facebook. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(2), 605-616.
36. Bajpai, N., Biberman, J., & Sharma, A. (2019). Information and Communications Technology in the Education Sector in India.
- 37 Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (1998). *Multivariate data analysis* (Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 207-219). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice hall.

Authors

Genimon V Joseph is a research scholar and faculty at Vimal Jyothi Institute of Management and Research, Chemperi, Kannur, India; post-graduated in MBA with Finance specialization, holds Post Graduate Diploma in Human Resource Management (PGDHRM), and National Eligibility Test (NET by UGC). He has presented many papers in international-national conferences and publications are on technology-based topics. His research interest is in digital Technology Adoption and its effective use in multiple scenarios. He had guided various PG projects and organization studies. He has teaching and administrative experience in MBA and Engineering Colleges since 2008. He is an active member of the International Association of Engineers (IAENG), Teaching and Education Research Association (TERA), Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE), Organization for Industrial-Spiritual and Cultural Advancement (OISCA) International, and other organizations for the cause of social justice and harmony. He held various management positions as Administrator to Vimal Jyothi Institutions, Academic council member, MESHAR trust advisory member, Vimal Jyothi welfare trust member, and Kerala Catholic Engineering College Management Association member. His areas of interest are institution branding, Management, and Engineering education, Research, Technology implementation, Human Resource Management, Insurance, public speaking, and social services.

Kennedy Andrew Thomas is the Director of the Centre for Education Beyond Curriculum (CEDBEC) and Professor in School of Education at Christ University, Bangalore, India. His Doctor of Philosophy, Master of Education and Bachelor of Education, are in Education from Bangalore University, and Master of Arts from Annamalai University, India. He has published 11 research articles in international and national journals and authored and edited books/chapters of reputable in nature. He is a resource person in fields of research, education, technology since 2011, and delivered multiple sessions and organized numerous national and international seminars every year under the CEDBEC, Christ (Deemed to be) University, Bangalore. He is a research supervisor for doctoral scholars and M.Phil. Researchers. He is an active member of multiple professional associations for the cause of research and education.